

BETA CALCULATION IN EMERGING MARKETS IN THE CROSS-BORDER CONTEXT – SELECTED PROBLEMS

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Abstract

When investing in emerging markets, investors face issues regarding the valuation of potential investments that may considerably affect the investment decision. This article discusses the challenges of valuing a company within the European emerging markets. We will focus on several issues regarding the reliability and fitness of Beta estimates with the use of peer groups in the context of cross-border investment valuation.

I. Introduction

In the context of cross-border valuations, the risk is often expressed as the cost of capital. Accurate estimation of an appropriate discount rate is therefore most important to all cross-border investment decisions. This issue goes to the heart of valuation in European emerging markets, whether the investor is a multinational company conducting a purchase price allocation of a recently acquired foreign entity or a medium size company establishing a joint venture in a neighbouring country.

Differences in risk and a lack of understanding of how emerging market returns are influenced by advanced markets and vice-versa, as well as a lack of statistically reliable historical data, are factors that all international managers and investors have to contend with. From a public policy point of view, determining the appropriate cost of equity is crucial in lowering the uncertainty that multinational companies (MNCs), local companies and public sector organisations face when investing in these countries.

Within the European integration process, great investment opportunities have arisen due to the wide availability of EU funds supporting cross-border cooperation initiatives. Thus, the significant increase in M&A activity could be observed in new accessions and mature European countries in recent years. As a result, the improvement in valuation techniques has gained a prominent place on the agenda of investors and financial analysts dealing with the region. However, the task entails substantial challenges. A fundamental

valuation requires the determination of an appropriate cost of capital, and the traditional capital asset pricing-based models (CAPM) normally used to compute it are difficult to apply in new accessions and candidate countries, as the majority of them are still in a transition and suffer from a lack of efficient markets.

This article addresses the challenge of how to calculate and properly apply the Betas in the process of valuing companies operating in the emerging markets. This paper will focus on cross-border investment valuations and review selected examples regarding the reliability and fitness of the estimated Betas. Our research is substantiated in the recent accession of many Eastern European countries to the EU. Our argument is supported by a thorough analysis of Betas calculated for companies headquartered in these new and prospective members countries of the EU.

II. Challenges of the Emerging Markets

A problem arises when the appropriate cost of equity is required to be assessed for the evaluation of a cross-border transaction within the EU, especially in the Central European region. The purpose of the cost of equity calculation is that it will aid the firm's management to make a financial decision in the best interests of its equity shareholders. The practical result of the theory as outlined above is that if a firm's cost of capital is held to be synonymous with the cost of capital to the shareholders, the firm, by accepting all investment opportunities offering a rate of return in excess of the shareholders' cost of capital, will improve their financial position by providing investments for their capital superior in yield to those obtainable elsewhere.

Peer group analysis

Several commonly accepted techniques are used to derive the cost of equity for companies operating in these emerging markets. One which is especially useful when the company is a non-quoted closely held entity is peer group analysis².

² J. Pettit, *The WACC User's Guide*, 2005. Available at Social Science Research Network.

In this approach we seek to determine the closest possible approximation for systematic risk by calculating an industry Beta. The underlying assumption is that the systematic risk is similar for all businesses in that industry and the way the business is financed is the major source of differentiation. Typically, a number of comparable peer group companies would be used to arrive at an estimate of the cost of equity for the analysed company, with their Betas being assumed to be relevant as indicators of market risk. A simple mean or median of pure-play comparable unlevered Betas may serve as a representative proxy for the company's unlevered Beta. The unlevered Beta is then relevered with the use of a target capital structure. Quite simply, the published Beta coefficients are adjusted to reflect the potential level of debt relevant to the analysed company.³

CAPM and Tax CAPM

The concept of Beta expressing the systematic risk of the underlying asset comes from one of the most popular methodologies, widely accepted by both practitioners and academics, which is the CAPM. According to classical CAPM, the relationship between risk and return is captured by a linear function, where risk is measured by the Beta. In other words, Beta measures the sensitivity of the returns for a particular stock to the returns on the market and is an essential element of the CAPM.

Another theoretical approach, the so-called Tax CAPM, requires accounting for income taxes in determining the cost of equity. Consequently, adoption of this approach implies a different recognition of financial incomes and dividends. Accounting for personal income tax in the process of a business valuation is quite controversial. However, it is worth mentioning that a specific law exists in several countries that requires the adoption of Tax CAPM, especially in the context of valuations for fiscal and statutory purposes.⁴ However, worldwide practices⁵ (such as International Valuation Standards [IVS]) do not

³ R.W. Mills, *The Dynamics of Shareholder Value*, Mars Business Associates Ltd, 1998.

⁴ Several countries have adopted this approach, such as Germany and the Czech and Slovak republics.

⁵ IVSC, *International Valuation Standards*, 2007, 8th edition.

consider personal income taxes. Therefore, this paper will not consider the Tax CAPM, which should be used for valuations incorporating personal income taxes.⁶

BETA calculation problems

Traditionally, Beta is derived by applying ordinary least squares (OLS) to realised historical returns on particular stock and a selected relevant index (benchmark). As a result we obtain a Beta coefficient that could be interpreted as a measure of the systematic risk (also known as market risk), expressing how changes in the market would affect the stock price.

Beta is used to adjust the required rate of return for the systematic risk attributable to each stock. One of the drawbacks of the traditional OLS estimate is the assumption that the Beta of emerging markets is stationary. It is obvious that no economic variable including the Beta coefficient is constant over time. However, for some purposes, an individual might be willing to act as if the values of Beta for individual securities were constant or stationary over time. For example, a person who wishes to assess the future risk of a target company's cash flow is really interested in the behaviour of averages of the Betas over time and not directly in the values appearing in the particular time intervals. Sharpe and Cooper⁷ assert that the high probability of falling into similar risk classes in successive periods indicates at least some stability in Beta. There is general agreement that although Betas are not stationary, they are to some extent predictable. Therefore, we would normally calculate straightforward historical Betas and apply them to forward-looking valuation models, providing the acceptance of the premises outlined above.

Mean reversion

The next challenge related to historical Beta estimates is that they are historical as opposed to forward-looking. There is evidence that Betas tend to regress to some long-

⁶ For Tax CAPM, refer to Brennan, "Taxes, market valuation and corporate financial policy", *National Tax Journal*; 1970, 417-427 and also D. Schmitt and F.T. Dausend, *Empirical Findings on the Tax CAPM for the German Capital Market*, 2007, available online at <http://ssrn.com/abstract=965476>

⁷ W.F. Sharpe, G.M. Cooper, "Risk-return classes of New York stock exchange common stocks, 1931-1967", *Financial Analysts Journal*; March/April 1972, 28(2).

run equilibrium value (usually the industry average).⁸ Consequently, historically estimated Betas are on average too small – they are biased towards zero. For example, even if all Betas in a market were truly equal to one, sampling errors could force the historical estimate to vary around one. Stock with a Beta below one would have a negative measurement error. There is, of course, no reason why we would expect it to have a negative measurement error again in the future. Our best guess is that the Beta would be one in the future. Thus, we would find that the Beta would regress back to the mean (that is, one). Even if true Betas are not all equal to one, statistically estimated Betas that are very small or very large will most probably have large negative or positive measurement errors.

Moreover, Dimson states that: “*infrequent trading will bias Beta estimates so as to cause the estimates to appear stable. Infrequently traded securities will have low Beta estimates, while frequently traded securities will have high estimates. Provided the frequency of trading is serially correlated, the Beta estimates will be a relatively stable, regressing somewhat to the mean*”.⁹ Similar evidence for small-stock in large markets has been found.¹⁰

However, in markets where there are insufficient numbers of shares to allow the portfolio theory to work properly, we can observe anomalies that could be perceived as an opportunity for share trading strategies but are non meaningful for the project appraisal or business enterprises valuation. Straightforward calculated Betas are negative for emerging markets. The simple interpretation of this fact is that these particular stocks move counter to the market. Although the inclusion of a stock which moves counter to the market can substantially reduce the risk of a portfolio,¹¹ the use of this result to construct the peer group for cost of capital derivation for non-quoted companies tends to

⁸ For the WACC calculation later in this paper we used the mean reversion adjustments suggested by Bloomberg, that is Adjusted Beta = (0.67) * RAW BETA + (0.33) * 1

⁹ E. Dimson, “Risk measurement when shares are subject to infrequent trading”, *Journal of Financial Economics*; 1979, 7(2).

¹⁰ R.G. Ibbotson, P.D. Kaplan, J.D. Peterson, “Estimates of small-stock betas are much too low”, *Journal of Portfolio Management*; 1997. A.W. Lo, A.C. MacKinlay, “An econometric analysis of nonsynchronous data”, *Journal of Econometrics*; 1990, 45.

¹¹ E.M. Blume, “On the assessment of risk”, *The Journal of Finance*; 1971, 36(1).

be inappropriate. By applying a negative Beta to CAPM, we would receive a cost of capital that is lower than the return on risk-free assets. Consequently, we would have to challenge the main premise of corporate finance that is the expectation that the equity is more risky and therefore more expensive than the debt; whereas, especially in this particular case, the cost of equity would be lower than the sovereign debt.

Later in this paper we will focus on three selected problems which, in our opinion, are crucial to the issue of cross-border valuations in the emerging markets.

Problem 1: R-squared in Beta calculation

The behaviour of R-squared causes interest among researchers and analysts. One of the interpretations concentrates on the fact that R-squared could be treated as a fitness indicator. That is to say that the higher the R-squared the stronger our claim could be that the Beta in a particular regression model reflects the stronger relationship between market and stock returns. However, it was also proved that in developed markets R-squareds tend to be low, as the proportion of the variance of returns explained by the market declines steadily in line with market development. In other words, the importance of the market factor decreases and the unsystematic risk is supposed to be responsible for the stock movements.¹²

Interestingly, R-squareds tend to be much higher in emerging markets than in developed markets (such as the US and the UK), providing they are calculated against local indices. This could be explained partly by the fact that there are fewer stocks in each emerging market, and supported by the observation that during periods of crisis all assets move together and hence correlations tend to increase.¹³

Sometimes the significant decrease of R-squareds can be explained by the impact of the outlier type of observations. Influential points and outliers need to be identified. Little confidence can be placed in regression results that have been dominated by a few

¹² Ibid.

¹³ M. Moussavian, *Global Emerging Equity Markets*, Credit Suisse First Boston, 2000.

observations, regardless of the total size of the study. This again is typical for emerging markets, where significant volatility tends to occur; sometimes additionally amplified by a sudden change in currency exchange rates (we will discuss this issue later). The first concern should be to verify that these data points are correct. Clearly identifiable errors should be corrected if possible or else eliminated from the dataset.¹⁴

Problem 2: Autocorrelation in Beta calculation

Another challenge that is frequently faced in the quest for a reliable Beta comes from the fact that we are dealing with time series which tend to have, by nature, a sequential order that is referred to as autocorrelation. This is a really serious problem due to the fact that one of the fundamental assumptions underlying the regression model is that the error terms associated with the subsequent observations are uncorrelated. Positive autocorrelation will result in an underestimation of the standard error of the estimated coefficients (Beta and Alpha). This in turn yields an inflated t ratio, which means that it is possible that coefficients will be found to be significantly different from zero when in fact they are not. As a result, Betas would be accepted instead of being rejected.¹⁵

Basically, there are two commonly adopted methods to detect autocorrelation: the so-called residual plots and the Durbin Watson test. A scatter plot can easily reveal serial correlation, where the error terms tend to be correlated showing an asymmetric (curved) pattern. Statistics offer several remedies for correcting autocorrelation, such as adjustment of the coefficient standard errors (e.g. Hanson method) and improvement of the specification of the model.¹⁶

According to pure CAPM theory, we should calculate the returns of our shares against the returns received from the market portfolio. That portfolio, which should contain all

¹⁴ J.O. Rawlings, S.G. Pentula, D.A. Dickey, *Applied Regression Analysis: a Research Tool*, 2nd edn., Springer-Verlag, New York, 1998.

¹⁵ S. Chatterjee, A.S. Hadi, *Regression Analysis by Example*, 4th edn., Wiley-Interscience, 2006.

¹⁶ R.A. Defusco, D.W. McLeavey, J.E. Pinto, D.E. Runkle, *Quantitative Methods for Investment Analysis*, Association for Investment Management and Research, USA, 2001, p.450 et sqq.

the marketable assets available to the investor, is in fact unobservable.¹⁷ For years, the most popular index to use was MSCI World, as it was believed to reflect the world market returns and thus be the best proxy for the market portfolio. Unfortunately, this approach would not bring the best results, not least due to the segmentation and incompleteness of the emerging markets that should act as solid constituents of the universal portfolio. What we are actually using is the so-called benchmark Beta computed against a component of the market portfolio.¹⁸ Consequently, what we receive is a Beta that should not be treated as if it is the true market Beta, but rather we should treat it as a Beta computed against the observable component of the true but unobservable market portfolio. Acceptance of this fact helps us to comfortably move into more familiar areas, such as the European market. For the purpose of this publication, we will adopt the market participant¹⁹ - industrial investor perspective, with the assumption that the European index stands well for the proxy of a locally well diversified market player. Consequently, we regress the returns of the shares from our selected peer group on the returns of the benchmark. The result should inform us about how much of the systematic risk will be added to our portfolio with the acquisition of the assets in question.

Problem 3: Currency exchange rates in Beta calculation

The last issue that we would like to discuss is the problem of currency exchange rates. For most theoreticians and practitioners, it is obvious that one cannot simply compare interest rates across bonds in different currencies.²⁰ However, it is common practice in the industry to accept the premise that by regressing the returns of a Polish company quoted in PLN at the Warsaw Stock Exchange on the DJ STOXX 600,²¹ quoted in EUR, one can obtain the Beta of this company reflecting the perspective of the Pan-European investor. Fine, when in the case of Poland there was no significant volatility in the EUR/PLN exchange rate observed, especially in the period covered by this research (May

¹⁷ J.Y. Campbell, A.W. Lo, C. McKinlay, *The Econometrics of Financial Markets*, Princeton University Press, New Jersey, 1997.

¹⁸ C.S. Eun, "The benchmark beta, CAPM, and pricing anomalies", *Oxford Economic Papers*, 1994, **46**(2).

¹⁹ J.T. Budyak, "Discount Rate Considerations-A Market Participant Perspective", *Valuation Strategies*, July/August, 2008.

²⁰ R.W. Mills, *The Dynamics ...*, op. cit.

²¹ Dow Jones STOXX Index is a broad based capitalization-weighted index of European stocks. The equities use free float shares in the index calculation.

2005 - May 2007), then in the case of Turkey, proper accounting for currency effects may pay off. Tables 4-6 present the results of appropriate accounting for currency effects in Pan-European Beta estimation. The situation becomes even more serious when the peer group built out of central and south European energy companies has to be created for the purpose of a potential acquisition planned by an energy company operating from a mature EU country.

III. Comparable Analysis of the Competitive Approaches to the Cost of Equity Capital Estimation in Emerging Markets

We have built our peer group upon the assumption that the potential target company is situated in a newly acceded EU country and the acquirer is a well diversified sectoral (energy) investor headquartered in a mature EU country. For the purpose of this exercise, we use pure play unlevered Betas calculated over a sample of two years' (May 2005 - May 2007) weekly data (approx 105 observations) as a proxy for the target's Beta.²² Next, we repeat the exercise over two more time intervals (May 2006 - May 2008 and May 2007 - May 2009).

The results for the straightforward calculated Betas are presented in Tables 1-3. Subsequently, Tables 4-6 show the results cleaned of currency effects and identified statistical issues. Then the test for significance of the regression coefficients was run and companies that did not pass these tests were removed from the peer group. The results were then used to derive the price per share using the Discounted Cash Flow method (based on the Free Cash Flow to Capital valuation model). This model appears to us as the most useful, bearing in mind that it concentrates on seven key value drivers and does not require thousands of lines within long spreadsheets.²³

As we were using the hypothetical energy company business model, we applied the 20/80 (D/E) capital structure, receiving the price of EUR 3.28 for straightforward calculated

²² This is a commonly used approach adopted by many business enterprise valuation consulting groups.

²³ R.W. Mills, *The Dynamics ...*, op. cit.

Betas and EUR 2.66 for currency adjusted data based on the data from the May 2005 - May 2007 interval.²⁴ The concluded impact of the currency mismatching and unadjusted raw data in the process of the cost of capital derivation on the final share price is about 23.5%. This difference should be carefully considered when the decision is made on how the currency should be treated in the cost of capital derivation, as the consequences of miscalculation may be severe.

Summary

The Discounted Cash Flow method is commonly used to determine whether to make an investment in a capital project, as well as in determining the value of a target company in a merger or cross-border acquisition transaction. Determination of the appropriate cost of capital is a necessary element in the Discounted Cash Flow model. The most commonly used technique for determining the cost of equity capital is the CAPM, which posits that the cost of equity capital is equal to the sum of (1) the risk-free rate and (2) the Beta for the investment multiplied by the market risk premium. Thus, the Beta is an essential element in CAPM and, therefore, is often an essential element in the Discounted Cash Flow model. Although the majority of market participants are fully equipped with highly sophisticated tools to help them derive Betas for any occasion, they should remain fully aware of the consequences of the blind misapplication of the right means. Professor Money makes a very useful comment on the misapplication of acknowledged theories, stating that there are people who make mistakes by applying the wrong theory (or applying it incorrectly) to solve a particular problem. The theory, if tested and accepted, is usually correct,²⁵ and this is exactly what we are trying to show. There are tools at hand that can help analysts calibrate Betas in their quest for Cost of Equity in emerging markets, but they have to be used thoroughly.

The CAPM is a very controversial concept and discussions around its appropriateness still attract equal numbers of supporters and opponents, specifically in the context of

²⁴ Consequently, the difference for the period May 2006 - May 2008, the time of stable markets growth, equaled 11.05% and for the interval including the crisis turmoil (May 2007 - May 2009) the difference reached 21.82%.

²⁵ A.H. Money, speech addressing the conferment of the Honorary Degree of Master of the College at Greenlands, 28 October 2006.

foreign investment appraisals. However, Chan and Lakonishok²⁶ point out that we might need decades of additional data before the CAPM can be *rejected* with statistical confidence. In fact, typical statistical results are often so weak and confidence intervals so wide that we cannot reject anything and, thus, conclude whether CAPM is right or wrong. The current turbulent environment produces market data that can only strengthen the historical confusion around CAPM theory.²⁷

The selected problems and remedies presented in this paper do not exhaust the subject of reliable Beta derivation for emerging markets, for the purpose of cross-border transactions. We strongly believe that there is still plenty of room for improvements which may be of value to analysts operating in emerging markets. We think here particularly of a few of the most problematic issues prevailing in emerging markets, such as low liquidity of stocks, synchronicity of prices and normality of distribution. But these are issues worth covering in separate articles.

²⁶ L.K.C. Chan, J. Lakonishok, "Are the reports of beta's death premature?", *Journal of Portfolio Management*, Summer, **19**(4).

²⁷ M. Goldman, "Market turmoil may require new ways to build up cost of capital", *The Value Examiner*, January/February, 2009.

Table 1

Staright forward Beta (mixed currencies, raw observations), May 2006 - May 2007											
TESTS											
Company Ticker	Raw	Adjusted	No. of observations	R ²	F test (linearity)			t-test (linearity confirmation)			
					F calculated	F (critical value)	Test result	t-Stat calculated	t-Stat (critical value)	p value	Test result
Zoren TI	0.51	0.67	105	0.01	1.4625	0.8235	Beta is significant	1.2093	1.9833	0.0500	Beta is not significant
Akenr TI	1.18	1.12	105	0.14	16.7674	0.8235	Beta is significant	4.0948	1.9833	0.0500	Beta is significant
Ayen TI	0.81	0.87	105	0.05	5.4211	0.8235	Beta is significant	2.3283	1.9833	0.0500	Beta is significant
PEP PW	1.47	1.31	105	0.15	18.1765	0.8235	Beta is significant	4.2634	1.9833	0.0500	Beta is significant
EMASZA HB	0.61	0.74	104	0.07	7.6774	0.8235	Beta is significant	2.7708	1.9835	0.0500	Beta is significant

Table 2

Staright forward Beta (mixed currencies, raw observations), May 2007 - May 2008											
TESTS											
Company Ticker	Raw	Adjusted	No. of observations	R ²	F test (linearity)			t-test (linearity confirmation)			
					F calculated	F (critical value)	Test result	t-Stat calculated	t-Stat (critical value)	p value	Test result
Zoren TI	0.36	0.57	105	0.02	1.6748	0.8235	Beta is significant	1.2941	1.9833	0.0500	Beta is not significant
Akenr TI	1.13	1.09	104	0.01	1.3435	0.8235	Beta is significant	1.1591	1.9835	0.0500	Beta is not significant
Ayen TI	0.81	0.87	104	0.10	11.3333	0.8235	Beta is significant	3.3665	1.9835	0.0500	Beta is significant
PEP PW	1.19	1.13	104	0.15	18.0000	0.8235	Beta is significant	4.2426	1.9835	0.0500	Beta is significant
EMASZA HB	0.66	0.77	104	0.12	13.9091	0.8235	Beta is significant	3.7295	1.9835	0.0500	Beta is significant

Table 3

Staright forward Beta (mixed currencies, raw observations), May 2008 - May 2009											
TESTS											
Company Ticker	Raw	Adjusted	No. of observations	R ²	F test (linearity)			t-test (linearity confirmation)			
					F calculated	F (critical value)	Test result	t-Stat calculated	t-Stat (critical value)	p value	Test result
Zoren TI	0.89	0.93	104	0.26	35.8378	0.8235	Beta is significant	5.9865	1.9835	0.0500	Beta is significant
Akenr TI	1.04	1.03	104	0.27	37.7260	0.8235	Beta is significant	6.1422	1.9835	0.0500	Beta is significant
Ayen TI	0.95	0.97	104	0.29	41.6620	0.8235	Beta is significant	6.4546	1.9835	0.0500	Beta is significant
PEP PW	0.30	0.53	104	0.06	6.5106	0.8235	Beta is significant	2.5516	1.9835	0.0500	Beta is significant
EMASZA HB	0.39	0.59	104	0.15	18.0000	0.8235	Beta is significant	4.2426	1.9835	0.0500	Beta is significant

Tables 4

Beta with tailored adjustments (one currency, transformed data where necessary), May 2006 - May 2007												
					TESTS							
					F test (linearity)			t-test (linearity confirmation)				
Company Ticker	Raw	Adjusted	No. of observations	R ²	F calculated	F (critical		t-Stat calculated	t-Stat		p value	Test result
						value)	Test result		(critical	value)		
Zoren TI	0.98	0.99	105	0.04	4.6280	0.8235	Beta is significant	2.1513	1.9830	0.0500	Beta is significant	
Akenr TI	1.66	1.44	105	0.19	24.1605	0.8235	Beta is significant	4.9153	1.9830	0.0500	Beta is significant	
Ayen TI	1.28	1.19	105	0.11	12.7303	0.8235	Beta is significant	3.5680	1.9830	0.0500	Beta is significant	
PEP PW	1.68	1.46	105	0.18	22.6098	0.8235	Beta is significant	4.7550	1.9830	0.0500	Beta is significant	
EMASZA HB	0.79	0.86	104	0.11	12.0940	0.8235	Beta is significant	3.4776	1.9833	0.0500	Beta is significant	

Tables 5

Beta with tailored adjustments (one currency, transformed data where necessary), May 2007 - May 2008												
					TESTS							
					F test (linearity)			t-test (linearity confirmation)				
Company Ticker	Raw	Adjusted	No. of observations	R ²	F calculated	F (critical		t-Stat calculated	t-Stat		p value	Test result
						value)	Test result		(critical	value)		
Zoren TI	0.81	0.87	105	0.07	7.7527	0.8235	Beta is significant	2.7844	1.9830	0.0500	Beta is significant	
Akenr TI	1.31	1.21	104	0.14	16.6047	0.8235	Beta is significant	4.0749	1.9833	0.0500	Beta is significant	
Ayen TI	1.28	1.19	104	0.11	12.6067	0.8235	Beta is significant	3.5506	1.9833	0.0500	Beta is significant	
PEP PW	1.36	1.24	104	0.18	22.3902	0.8235	Beta is significant	4.7318	1.9833	0.0500	Beta is significant	
EMASZA HB	0.87	0.91	104	0.16	19.4286	0.8235	Beta is significant	4.4078	1.9833	0.0500	Beta is significant	

Tables 6

Beta with tailored adjustments (one currency, transformed data where necessary), May 2008 - May 2009												
					TESTS							
					F test (linearity)			t-test (linearity confirmation)				
Company Ticker	Raw	Adjusted	No. of observations	R ²	F calculated	F (critical		t-Stat calculated	t-Stat		p value	Test result
						value)	Test result		(critical	value)		
Zoren TI	1.26	1.17	104	0.38	62.5161	0.8235	Beta is significant	7.9067	1.9833	0.0500	Beta is significant	
Akenr TI	1.43	1.29	104	0.38	62.5161	0.8235	Beta is significant	7.9067	1.9833	0.0500	Beta is significant	
Ayen TI	1.32	1.21	104	0.39	65.2131	0.8235	Beta is significant	8.0755	1.9833	0.0500	Beta is significant	
PEP PW	0.60	0.73	104	0.18	22.3902	0.8235	Beta is significant	4.7318	1.9833	0.0500	Beta is significant	
EMASZA HB	0.65	0.77	104	0.29	41.6620	0.8235	Beta is significant	6.4546	1.9833	0.0500	Beta is significant	